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PREPARATION OF A SORBENT BASED ON SUNFLOWER WASTE

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ABSTRACT

The presented article is related to the research on water purification from various types of pollutants, and is dedicated to the preparation method of activated carbon-containing sorbents made from the sunflower plant. The raw material obtained from the sunflower hat was crushed and modified with various acids and hydrogen peroxide. Some physical and physicochemical properties of carbonized samples were studied. Using chromatographic, spectral, gravimetric and potentiometric analysis methods, the structure of sorbents, particle size distribution, specific surface area, and sorption capacity were determined. It was determined that the prepared samples have 2 times lower scattering density than activated carbon recommended in the composition of water filters in the industry as a comparison material. Depending on the density of the selected modifier and the carbonization temperature, the content of total and water-soluble ash varies in direct proportion. The granulometric composition of the obtained materials is represented by particles with a diameter of 40.62-772.19 microns; Concord between surface area and electrokinetic potential of materials for dye sorption was studied. Based on the quantitative values of the surface areas, it can be said that the samples belong to micro-mesoporous materials.

Keywords: sorbent, sunflower hat, plant waste, activated carbon, carbonization, water treatment, reuse

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ПРИГОТОВЛЕНИЕ СОРБЕНТА НА ОСНОВЕ ОТХОДОВ ПОДСОЛНЕЧНИКА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Представленная статья связана с исследованиями по очистке воды от различных видов загрязнителей и посвящена способу приготовления сорбентов, содержащих активированный уголь из растений подсолнечника. Сырье, полученное с грядки подсолнечника, измельчали и

модифицировали различными кислотами и перекисью водорода. Исследованы некоторые физические и физико-химические свойства карбонизированных образцов. С помощью хроматографических, спектральных, гравиметрических и потенциометрических методов анализа определяли структуру сорбентов, гранулометрический состав, удельную поверхность и сорбционную емкость. Определено, что приготовленные образцы имеют в 2 раза меньшую насыпную плотность, чем активированный уголь, рекомендуемый в составе фильтров для воды в промышленности в качестве материала сравнения. В зависимости от плотности выбранного модификатора и температуры карбонизации содержание общей и водорастворимой золы изменяется прямо пропорционально. Гранулометрический состав полученных материалов представлен частицами диаметром 40,62-772,19 мкм. Изучена корреляция между площадью поверхности и электрокинетическим потенциалом материалов для сорбции красителей. По количественным значениям площадей удельной поверхности можно сказать, что образцы относятся к микромезопористым материалам.

Ключевые слова: сорбент, растительные отходы, шляпка подсолнечника, активированный уголь, карбонизация, очистка воды, повторное использование

At present, drinking water has become a commercial object in many countries. Developed European countries such as Germany, the Netherlands, and Denmark buy drinking water from Sweden. In Japan, stores sell bottled water from Norway, while Hong Kong receives water through a pipeline through the territory of the People's Republic of China. Saudi Arabia buys drinking water from the Philippines and Singapore from Malaysia by tankers. In recent decades, the pollution of water and water bodies has become a source of increasing problems on a global scale. One of the most effective methods of water purification is based on the ability of sorbent materials to absorb various pollutants. The water purification process is carried out in the following sequence: coagulation → rinsing → filtration → sorption.

Activated carbon is widely used as a sorbent in water purification filters. The activated carbon production process consists of two stages: pyrolysis (carbonization) and activation. After pyrolysis, a product with low ash content and microporous structure is obtained by steam activation; carbon with micro- and meso-cavities is obtained by chemical activation. The amount of pores is determined by the method of activation [1]. Recently, as sorbents, active carbon obtained from the waste of plant raw materials - beet pulp, rice, buckwheat, walnut, fruit and sunflower seed husks - has been used more frequently. The main advantages of this option are ease of use, efficiency, possibility of using secondary raw materials, environmental cleanliness and low cost of raw materials [2-6]. Despite the fact that sunflower oil is mainly imported from foreign countries, the production of this oil is organized in Azerbaijan (e.g. Agstafa, Ivanovka, etc.) and more than 40 thousand tons of refined sunflower oil are produced every year.

The waste of this production is used for the production of fodder in poultry farming, and the rest is thrown into landfills [7]. Literature studies show that although there are very few interesting works in this field, it is possible to find them. It is possible to adsorb about 90% of heavy metal ions in water and clean the soil contaminated with oil and lubricants by means of activated carbon prepared using sunflower seed and bed [8-11]. In the presented study, a sorbent was prepared using sunflower seeds and seed pods, and some physical and physicochemical properties of this sorbent were studied.

1M, 3M and 10M chloride, nitrate, sulfate, orthophosphoric acid and hydrogen peroxide solutions were used for modification. Modification solutions were prepared in the laboratory using reagents in different molar concentrations according to the methodology [8,12]. To study the structure and particle size distribution of the samples obtained from the charring process, to determine the specific surface area using scanning electron microscopy, spectral and chromatographic analysis methods were used to determine the sorption capacity of dye (methylene blue) and acetic acid. A gravimetric analysis method was used to determine the bulk density of total and water-soluble ash. The sunflower plant reserve selected for the experiment was cleaned and dried. 100 grams of waste accurately weighed with an analytical scale was crushed to 1-2 cm size in a laboratory shredder. Shredded waste was placed in a 3-liter plastic container with a diameter of 30 cm, 0.8 l of modifying

solution was added to it, and the plastic was mixed with a spoon. The mixture was kept for 4 hours with occasional stirring. After that, the solution was filtered into a porcelain cup with a volume of 1 l, the mouth was closed with a porcelain lid, placed in a metal reactor with a gas-retaining tube, a muffle furnace, and the carbonization process was carried out by heating the furnace from 200°C to 650°C for 2 hours. After the process is completed, the porcelain beaker is removed from the muffle furnace, the contents are emptied into a 1 l glass beaker and washed with distilled water until a neutral reaction is obtained (monitoring with universal indicator paper). The samples were completely dried in a drying cabinet for 12 hours at 105°C. Carbonized samples without modification were also prepared according to the same methodology. Also, industrial grade activated carbon was used as a reference material.

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The obtained activated carbon samples are in solid form, powdery particles whose color varies from dark brown to black. The mass of the modifying solution used per gram of the primary raw material varies depending on its density. Table 1 shows the correspondingly calculated mass of modifiers used for 10 grams of plant raw materials.

For comparison, we used natural gray coal and activated carbon used in industrial filters. The degree of charring was determined by weighing sunflower waste before and after charring according to the following formula:

$$R = C_{\tau} / C_0 \cdot 100\%,$$

Here, C_0 - until carbonization; C_{τ} is the mass after carbonization. The difference in carbonization rate is defined as: $\Delta R = 100\% - R$ [11].

The adsorption activity of the obtained samples was determined based on the density of the amount of methylene blue dye absorbed from the solution by the sunflower sample according to the known methodology [13].

Table 1.

Modifier used in raw materials (mass, g)

№	Modifier solution	The molar concentration of the solution(mol/l)	Mass of consumed substance (g)
1.	HNO ₃	1	5,04
2.		3	15.12
3.		10	50.41
4.	H ₂ SO ₄	1	7.84
5.		3	23.52
6	HCl HCl	10	78.40
7.		1	2.92
8.		3	8.76
9.		10	29.18
10.	H ₃ PO ₄	1	7.84
11.		3	23.51
12.		10	78.39
13.	H ₂ O ₂	1	2.72
14.		3	8.16
15.		10	27.21

In the series of H₂O₂ samples, the following regularity is observed: increasing the concentration of the modifier increases the area of the sorption surface. Carbonized samples at different temperature ranges (200°C, 350°C, and 650°C) show almost identical results in terms of

sorption efficiency (~26 mg/g) after 2.5 h of initiation of sorbent : sorbate contact using nitric acid. The specific surface area of the obtained coal samples was determined using an LXM-8 MD Chrome 5 gas chromatograph with an ionizing flame detector, with a low polarizing column (column dimensions 30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm, operating temperature range 60-350°C). has been done. The scattering density of the obtained activated carbons (mass density $\rho=0.95$, $n=3$ at $t=24^{\circ}\text{C}$) was determined. It was determined that the mass density of the obtained materials is on average 2 times less than the reference samples and ranges from 0.143 to 0.657 g/cm³. The amount of both total and water-soluble ash is an important indicator. The presence of high content of mineral components in coal used for sorption purposes can prevent the interaction of sorbates with active centers on the coal surface, polyvalent metal cations, as well as their oxides, can act as catalysts and lead to changes in activated carbon. The sorbed organic molecules, ash components can prevent the penetration of sorbates into the coal pores. Quantitative content of total and water-soluble ash in prepared activated carbon samples, as well as in comparison samples, was determined experimentally. With the increase in the concentration of the modifier and the increase in the carbonation temperature, the pH indicators of the environment for all samples, except for the samples treated with orthophosphoric acid solutions, change from strongly acidic to alkaline values. In samples treated with phosphoric acid solutions, a decrease in pH value (acidic environment) is observed with an increase in the concentration of the modifier and the temperature of carbonization; Based on the research, it can be concluded that:

The scattering density of modified coals is approximately 2 times lower than that of the compared activated coal and ranges from 0.145 to 0.659 g/cm³; The content of total and water-soluble ash increases with increasing modifier concentration and carbonization temperature; The granulometric composition of the obtained materials is represented by particles with a diameter of 60.26-770.92 microns; The area of the sorption surface for methylene blue dye is between 11.37 and 109.71 m²/g and varies depending on the values of the electrokinetic potential of the materials. For benzene sorption, the surface area varies between 3059 and 99555 m²/g; Based on the values of methylene blue absorption, the optimal contact time of the sorbent with sorbate was determined; Thus, the obtained active carbons belong to micro-mesoporous materials, based on the results, it was once again confirmed. The spent sorbent does not require regeneration costs, can be used as a valuable feed for livestock, and can be used as a fiber source, filler, etc. in grain feed mixtures as widely used.

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